

Educational Commons Facilitating Student Voice: An Ethnographic Approach

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Educational commons is an emergent paradigm that introduces participatory and democratic learning practices and governance, contrasting neoliberal and self-reliant approaches. Learning is seen as a common good, and so are the educational processes. This article presents evidence from the EU Horizon 2020 funded project SMOOTH and examines two distinct learning environments in Estonia: a non-formal education creativity accelerator and a democratic public school. These two contexts are explored to understand how educational commons are implemented in order to facilitate students' voice and agency. Drawing from ethnographic research, participants' narratives, and researchers' observations, the findings are analysed through the Lundy model of participation. The findings demonstrate that the practice of educational commons, or commons-based activities, inherently promotes students' voice and calls for safe and free spaces, while also reinforcing cooperation and responsibility among peers and the wider community. The findings shape implications for practice that envision learning as a shared resource created from the bottom-up and peer-governed. This approach aims for a perspective on education that is both created by, with, and for youth.

Keywords: educational commons, student voice, democratic education, non-formal education, Lundy framework of child participation

Introduction

I think I have been coming to VIVITA for 5 years now. When I was about 11 years old my mom told me that there will be a new space created where you can do things like 3D printing and cool projects and ... And in the beginning, I was like that ... this does not sound like possible. Why should someone let the children do all of that? And you know, it really is like that. You can do everything here; it is so supportive and friendly. And you learn so much through doing it yourself ... you are not just reading to memorise it hard like in school, here you learn many different things, so naturally and you will remember it. (participant quote, focus group interview 06.2022).

The quote above by a young person refers to the shortcomings of schooling as it is mostly organised today, focusing on memorisation practices, competition, national test examinations, and standardised curricula. However, the youth need to be able to explore

and realise their own interests (Estes 2004) to put into practice more actively what they have learned and think outside the box, looking for their own solutions. In this sense, this quote by a young learner highlights criticisms that neoliberal models of education have focused on creating a generation of self-reliant workforce by standardising schooling, promoting test-centric practices, and, at all costs, almost avoiding to provide the tools for youth's development of critical thinking, aiming beyond a solely self-provisioned entrepreneur as the aim of education (Pereira 2018). In line with these ideas, in the current article, the authors embark on the discovery of practices that can enhance student participation and agency. This is done primarily by looking at the practice of educational commons as participatory and democratic learning governance, contrasting neoliberal and self-reliant practices (Korsgaard 2019), with a view to facilitate students' voice and agency (Lundy 2007).

Commons is the social practice of co-creating and co-managing a resource, from our grandfathers' communal grazing fields to today's digital commons, like Wikipedia. Commons are characterised by different motivations, patterns, and rules than the dominant way of social reproduction, based on the maximisation of self-profit and hierarchical structures. Instead, the Commons bring forward the values of horizontal collaboration, sharing, transparency, and direct democracy. In fact, the Commons, also known as 'common-pool resources' or 'commons-based peer production', introduce a principle of social organisation and collective activities for social and natural activities and goods to be created, governed, and shared as a common resource by communities. In doing so, egalitarian and horizontal participation become the way to include all the people involved in such common resources and actions into shared decision-making, while calling into question established class, racial, gender inequalities, and all kinds of hierarchies (Pechtelidis and Kioupkiolis 2020).

In the same line, educational commons is a social practice that proposes both educators and students relinquish the traditional roles to equally participate and co-create their educational journey in common. As iterated earlier, most students do feel disconnected from the curriculum, while standardisation stifles their interests, limiting options to impact their own educational processes as agents of their learning. Hence, the first section of this article describes the Lundy model of participation (Lundy 2007), followed by an overview of the commons in educational settings, as these two form the key theoretical frame of current explorations.

The following section describes the SMOOTH project, funded under the EU Horizon 2020 programme, and its two case studies that have been implemented in Tallinn, the capital of Estonia: (1) Suvemäe-TKG, a democratic education-based branch within a local public school, and (2) VIVITA, a non-formal education creativity accelerator for young people. The third section presents and analyses both facilitators and participants' narratives, researchers' observations during the fieldwork process (based on the diaries and interviews implemented during the SMOOTH research project) and tries to draw connections between the process of commoning education and the promotion and operationalisation of the student voice according to the Lundy model. Finally, the conclusions review relationships between the educational commons and the promotion of student voice, potential limitations, and future research possibilities.

We draw our findings from these contexts based on the concept of educational commons and Lundy's model of participation (Lundy 2007), which prioritises and activates youth's voice and agency in learning environments and within the wider community. Unlearning or rethinking education through commoning terms and how it is currently enacted (Collet-Sabé and Ball 2022) seems a crucial next step to escaping modern individualistic, often decontextualised forms of education and enriching in

essence the plethora of EU and national directives that argue for students' empowerment via participatory and democratic processes. In doing so, reframing relationships between teachers and students is one of the key aspects (Blaikie, Daigle, Vasseur 2020; De Lissovoy 2011), paving the way for further participatory approaches as described with the Lundy model.

The research question that drives this study is: How are the essential elements of the Lundy model of participation — the space, voice, audience, and influence — visible, operationalised, and enhanced in the educational commons-based activities? In addition, the evidence gathered throughout the SMOOTH project and its two distinct case studies — each with a duration of three months — implemented in Estonia between 2022 and 2023 in the frame of the EU Horizon 2020 programme. The study draws on the researchers' observations during the fieldwork stage, as well as the participants' interviews. The next sections will briefly refer to the four elements of the Lundy model of participation and provide insights into educational commons as viewed in this study.

Literature Review

The Lundy Model of Participation

According to Adam Fletcher (2017), renowned writer and advocate of children's rights, the only way towards a truly meaningful involvement of young people is through their engagement as partners in every decision that affects them and their (learning) environments. The ultimate goal, Fletcher argues, is to improve social conditions and strengthen community development and democracy. The significance of the community in education has been reflected in the works of many authors, such as Dewey and Vygotsky, highlighting that learning is a social, rather than individualistic, perspective

(Osterman, 2000). However, it has been argued that schools often adopt organisational practices that neglect and undermine students' experience of participation (ibid).

Youth involvement in decision-making within schools has been associated with various advantages, as discussed elsewhere (Moreno Romero 2022). These include the enhancement of moral reasoning skills (Kohlberg 2013), a decrease in school abuse stemming from power imbalances (Delval and Lomelí 2013), the establishment of positive boundaries (Juul 2001), the reinforcement of a sense of belonging leading to increased commitment to learning, reduced anxiety, and the promotion of autonomy and self-regulation (Anderman 2002).

Additionally, benefits encompass improvements in students' argumentative abilities and academic performance (Bouché Peris 2003; Day et al. 2009), the fostering of participatory leadership cultures (Louis et al. 2010), the cultivation of attitudes valuing diversity and social commitment (Bruyere 2010), and the acquisition of knowledge about rights and responsibilities through practical experiences (Danner and Jonyiene 2012). Respectful attitudes towards diversity, and finally, citizen involvement through the feeling of empowerment and critical thinking processes during decision-making (Prud'homme 2014).

Likewise, it has been suggested that involving young people in age-mixed decision-making experiences promotes scaffolding (Vygotsky 1978) and guided participation and appropriation (Rogoff 2003). In these experiences, 'more competent' participants in the shared decision-making practice share with others appropriate discursive tools to, for example, participate, speak, take turns, and actively listen to other people.

On the other hand, some authors have pointed out some risks when inclusion in decision-making is limited or cosmetic. For example, when children's participation is limited to expressing their opinion in relation to the manipulated formulation of issues, without having real power to make decisions (Percy-Smith and Taylor 2008). Whenever there is potential adult manipulation of children's opinions, leaving little opportunity for them to formulate new ideas (Hecht 2010; Thornberg 2010); or when passive participatory models take place, such as representation or consultation (Lúcio and I'Anson 2015).

Founded on the adoption of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) by the UN General Assembly in 1989, Professor Laura Lundy from Queen's University has advocated a more inclusive and systematic approach to young people's participation in their learning environments and their communities. In her proposal, Lundy foresees a participatory model setting four elements to guarantee young people's right to freely express their views in all matters affecting them, as established by Article 12 of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child.

With the clear goal of providing guidance to decision-makers, administrators, and teachers, the Lundy model of participation invites schools and adults in general to listen to children and young people by including them in decision-making processes. In other words, this approach intends to facilitate 'participation with purpose' (Welty and Lundy 2013), meaning that young people's involvement in decision-making sets mechanisms for their views to be listened to, taken seriously, and given the proper importance to advance an outcome or change.

The four elements in the Lundy model of participation are set in a logical chronological order: space, voice, audience, and influence. Firstly, a space that guarantees

safe and inclusive opportunities for children to form and express their opinions needs to be created. Within this dimension, key actors are asked to consider, identify, and facilitate steps to involve young people, make their participation sustainable, include all actors involved in the issue, ensure the accessibility of the process, establish mechanisms to help young people feel safe and comfortable expressing their views, and develop tools to help those who might feel anxious or uncomfortable.

Secondly, the model invites stakeholders to identify and set the conditions for young people to use their voice and express their views, feelings, and perceptions. In this regard, a list of topics on which young people will share their views will be created, making sure mechanisms to keep the discussion centred are available, sharing with young people that participation is voluntary and withdrawal is available at any moment, facilitating age-appropriate and accessible information for young people to share their views, establishing collaboratively various ways to express themselves as needed, and helping them identify topics for discussion.

Thirdly, an audience needs to be committed to listen to young people's views seriously and proactively. Relatedly, adults are asked to identify steps to inform young people who, how, and when their opinions need to be shared, adults' degree of commitment to learn about and take young people's opinions into consideration, further involvement of appropriate decision-makers, the ways in which young people's opinions will be recorded in a youth-friendly way and allow for their verification that their opinions have been appropriately recorded, and strategies to help children participate in expressing their own opinions.

Finally, the participatory exercise needs to ensure influence to translate young people's voices to action, as appropriate. Within this realm, facilitators are asked to

describe the ways in which the youth will be informed about their reach and limitations in decision-making, provide feedback mechanisms during the development of policy or reform, highlight plans to ensure their views have an impact on decisions, set ways in which feedback will be provided as to how their views are used and related reasons in decision-making, and provide opportunities to evaluate the whole process with them.

Educational Commons & the SMOOTH Project

Commons and Commoning in Education

The word ‘common’ can have a negative meaning, deriving from what we identify as ordinary, non-innovative, or boring. However, the word comes from the 14th century ‘land held in common’ and ‘belonging to all’ (Online Etymology Dictionary, s.v. ‘common’, as in Tomašević et al. 2018). The root of the word can be traced even earlier, in Ancient Rome, where ‘communis’ meant something that is shared by many (Online Etymology Dictionary, s.v. ‘common’). Also, according to Tomašević et al., ‘Lipietz stresses that the Latin word ‘communis’ was coined from Latin words “munus”, meaning both “gift” and “duty”, and “com”, meaning “together”’ (Tomašević et al. 2018, 17). Hence, it is a word that carries a heavy and multiform historical load, mostly with a taste of togetherness, with the rights and responsibilities that this entails. These expressions and practices of cooperation and horizontality through the commons come far before modernity. As Arvidsson points out, commons are a ‘powerful source of alternative lifestyles and social movements’ (Arvidsson 2020, 1), from the European Late Middle Ages up to now, which point towards new seed forms of producing value and social change (Arvidsson 2020).

During the 1980s and 1990s, Elinor Ostrom, with her groundbreaking research, brought forward cases where up to 15,000 people managed a natural resource in a

commons-based way. Her research proved that all around the world, natural commons existed for generations that successfully managed their livelihoods (Ostrom 1990). Since the '90s, Ostrom's findings opened the discussion around the commons in which a multidisciplinary spectrum of researchers and activists got interested. Relevant to the purposes of this paper, it is worth mentioning that critical theory of the commons and relational theory of the commons broadened and deepened Ostrom's perspective from focusing merely on natural resources and small-scale communities to pointing out that commons emerge wherever people demand and act towards collective decision-making and collective management of resources, which can be physical, digital, cultural, and so on (Tomašević et al. 2018, De Angelis et al. 2014). This is a way to perceive commons as a transformative movement that aims to further democratise society, not focusing on the co-management of static resources but looking into co-creation and co-management as a dynamic social practice (Tomašević et al. 2018).

Since then, an expansion of practising and studying the social phenomenon of commoning has manifested in the physical, digital, and cultural sphere. Only to mention a few examples, we can pinpoint the multiverse of open-source, commons-based initiatives, such as Wikipedia, the free online encyclopaedia, Apache web server (Bauwens, Kostakis, and Pazaitis 2019), the social movements for the freedom of the internet, such as Free Assange & Free Snowden (Anderson 2022), or the Aaron Swartz case about open science and knowledge commons (Da Silveira 2013). Moreover, environmental social movements have been based on the commons, such as the Leave it in the Ground (Carter and McKenzie 2020), Degrowth (Kallis 2011), or the Right to the City movement (Mattei and Quarta 2015). Within this multiverse where people freely collaborate to reclaim, co-create, and co-manage resources, the discussion for education as a commons is still in its infancy, whereas of equal importance in the struggle towards

democratic societies and the reappropriation and transformation of education.

According to Dellenbaugh, the process of commoning, as characterised by many scholars, is defined by three pillars: 1. Resource, 2. Community, and 3. Institutions (Dellenbaugh et al. 2015, 13). This is to emphasise that we need to have a community (no. 2) — whether locally or digitally distributed, or both — that gathers around a resource (no. 1), creating rules and organisational forms (no. 3) in order to produce shared value. These groups of people share ‘the same values, norms, and needs’ (Tomašević et al. 2018, 48), so they create a common imaginary, either in a more concrete or more loose way (e.g. commoners in a neighbourhood managing a natural resource or commoners around the world creating and managing a digital resource).

Moreover, Silke Helfrich (as in Hopkins 2012) proposes three normative criteria in order to identify commons. Such criteria need to follow the co-management of a resource to be called commons: sustainable use, fair access, and collective control. Pechtelidis and Kioupkiolis (2020, 4), in the same line with Helfrich, describe that ‘the “common” habitus consists of (a) direct engagement in public and collective life, (b) autonomy, (c) self-reliance, and (d) equity’. Hence, commons can be seen as a dynamic social practice on how to govern in a collective, fair, and sustainable way both a resource, a community, and the institutions that the community sets in order for this collective governance to be functional and fruitful (Tomašević et al. 2018; Pechtelidis and Kioupkiolis, 2020).

When education and the learning process are seen under the prism of the commons, they become a collective good that is co-created and co-regulated by all involved (Pechtelidis 2023). They become a set of values in which children ‘are considered capable of making decisions and shaping their daily lives’ (Pechtelidis 2023,

5). The next section outlines how the educational commons are defined and implemented in the SMOOTH project that this study draws empirical findings from. The research contexts and their unique characteristics are also outlined in relation to the commons.

The SMOOTH Project

The SMOOTH project¹ explores how the commons could be embedded in educational settings. The educational commons is about sharing space for collaboration, content creation, socialisation, governance, playing, and learning. The ultimate goal of the SMOOTH project is to examine whether integrating the educational commons has an effect on reversing inequalities in education, strengthening ties with the wider community, and creating spaces of democratic citizenship.

The SMOOTH research team, which includes researchers from eight European countries, has developed strategies and training sessions for adults on how to develop and facilitate educational common spaces, also via the use of convivial tools and open technologies (Illich 1975). A variety of educational settings, spanning from schools and museums to NGOs and social spaces, were involved in this project and actively participated towards co-developing with the researchers' case studies through which the notions of commons were either integrated purposefully or explored in situ.

The current study is based on research undertaken by the Ragnar Nurkse Department of Innovation and Governance of Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech) and presents evidence and discusses findings from the Estonian context. While

¹ The SMOOTH project (GRANT NUMBER 101004491) proposes an innovative action research programme engaging children and youth to reverse inequalities that children and youth of vulnerable social groups face. It will reinforce intercultural and intergenerational dialogue and social integration, develop essential social and personal skills for both children, youth, and adults, establish spaces of democratic citizenship, and build and support the community through differences. SMOOTH will also perform a cross-cutting and cross-disciplinary analysis of educational commons. For further information, see <https://smooth-ecs.eu/>

one of the case studies, VIVITA, focuses on non-formal learning during the ‘extra-curricular time’ after school, the other one, Suvemäe-TKG, operates within formal education but adopts non-formal learning strategies. However, they both share the view that learning needs to be active and self-driven and that new positive relational patterns are fundamental and required in learning processes, for which they exploit a wide variety of different methodologies, consolidating them as innovators within the Estonian educational landscape.

Richer contextual information of each third party is presented in the next section. It is worth mentioning here that the findings of this study are not presented in an effort to juxtapose two different contexts: formal versus non-formal education, but rather that the particularities, idiosyncrasies, and affordances of each context are necessary to offer thick descriptions of events and practices and to further contextualise the interpretations made.

Context and Methodology

VIVITA - Contextual information

Figure 1: VIVITA, a non-formal education creativity accelerator for children and youth aged 9-15 years. [Photo is the courtesy of Tallin Music Week and VIVITA, taken from: <https://vivistop-telliskivi.medium.com/tallinn-music-week-x-vivita-kids-festival-438451f9c488>]

VIVITA is a youth creativity accelerator for children aged 9 to 15 years, which is part of a global network currently operating in eight countries: Estonia, Japan, Lithuania, New Zealand, Philippines, Singapore, South-Korea and the United States². Within each of these locations, VIVITA's physical learning centres are called 'Vivistops', with its Tallinn outlet³ having been opened in 2018. The VIVITA concept identifies itself as a 'no teachers-no curriculum' pedagogical approach, aiming at increasing the confidence of children and young people through their facilitated participation in various activities such as woodwork, 3D printing, handicraft, and cooking.

In order to reach its aims and provide diverse learning opportunities, VIVITA operates through a wide variety of different activities, like the 'free flow' activities that take place in open workshop areas (makerspace), where kids can work on their own projects with the support of adults, if required. Considering the specificity of the makerspace, safety instructions are of vital importance and are introduced to participants from the very first introductory visits. From the perspective of young participants, this represents trust from adults while building on an exciting experience to work with such tools, learning to keep safety in mind.

The team of VIVITA is composed of professional producers, passionate designers, and experienced engineers, currently totalling 12 people (at the time of writing

² <https://www.vivita.global/>

³ <https://www.vivita.ee/en>

the article), who are supported by experts from different fields in various projects. As a result of this, in addition to the 'free flow', there are more curated programmes. For example, the educational programme 'The Social Club' (Vivita Estonia 2022), which was the subject of the case study in VIVITA and was launched in 2021, inviting children and young people to form a small community on a voluntary basis and engage in organising a kids' festival in cooperation with Tallinn Music Week. In line with the pedagogical concept of VIVITA, the whole idea of the kids' festival and its operationalisation are driven by children and young people themselves, with adults taking a role of supportive and inspiring mentors on the learning journey.

Within the framework of the SMOOTH project, one VIVITA educator with a leading facilitation role was involved, as well as other team members and one representative from the Tallinn Music Week. The researcher joined the group throughout the process, both in their meetings and in their community WhatsApp chat, with the aim to document the process as well as to explore if and how the core principles of educational commons and participants' voice present and realised in such a learning process.

Suvemäe-TKG - Contextual information

Figure 2: Suvemäe-TKG, a democratic education branch in Tallinn Art Gymnasium;
photo by researcher

The second case study is Suvemäe-TKG, a democratic education-based branch⁴ within Tallinn Art Gymnasium, a municipal (public) school located in the Northern area of the Estonian capital⁵. Suvemäe-TKG was founded in 2019 as a pilot project of democratic education within the municipal school, implementing pedagogical principles focused on supporting young people's mental health and building a balance between the State academic requirements and students' own interests and vocations. Currently, Suvemäe-TKG serves 72 children and youth from 7 to 16 years of age (1-9 classes), and its staff is composed of a team of 4 full-time paid teachers, two support teachers and 2 part-time specialists (language, science, social pedagogue), who support students in their academic

⁴ The pedagogical principles associated with 'democratic education' are shared decision-making practices, self-directed learning, age-mixing and free play/time.

⁵ <https://suvemae.ee/> <https://kunst.edu.ee/suvemae/>

responsibilities, while involving them in decision-making and co-creating non-formal learning activities of their choice.

As a democratic education-based branch within Tallinn's Art Gymnasium, Suvemäe-TKG facilitates various learning methodologies and practices that are co-created, co-designed and co-evaluated with learners according to their skills and preferences. To start with, students get together twice a week in two different groups: classes 1-4 and classes 5-9 (although younger kids occasionally join the older kids' meeting and vice versa) to share information about events or learning opportunities, make decisions about the school life, propose activities and solve conflicts. These groups were initially set up by adults with the aim of 'modelling' the practice of facilitating an inclusive circle where everyone has a right to express their voice and use their vote. However, the meetings are nowadays run entirely by learners, providing opportunities for young people to take control and ownership over the school life and, in turn, model their practice to other students.

Within the framework of the SMOOTH project, Suvemäe-TKG students used this time to engage in building a Kitchen Island in the Creative (Arts) Room and a Zen Garden next to the schoolhouse thanks to funding available by the SMOOTH project. The project lasted around 8 weeks, had around 15 working meetings and counted with the voluntary participation of 8 young people (4 participants per project) and the support of two Suvemäe-TKG facilitators. The findings section further discusses the activities of this student-led research project.

Research Methodology and instruments

The ethnographic research approach followed in this project was conducted via fieldwork and involved researchers in conducting participant observations, interviews, and

pedagogical documentation with both facilitators or educators and youth or student participants in these two educational contexts. The study has received approval from the Ethics Committee of Tallinn University of Technology. Informed consent was acquired for all research participants involved.

Participant observation became a fundamental tool for making sense of the learning and accompaniment processes inherent to the commoning of learning experiences, generating practical and theoretical reflections formulated as interpretative theories (Jorgensen 1989; Kimball 1974). Fieldnotes were kept during observations and interviews were conducted, trying to capture in as much detail and provide thick descriptions of participants' behaviours and interactions. Fieldnotes also offered a description of the learning environment in an effort to contextualise the data as accurately as possible. Fieldnotes allow ethnographers to record happenings in learning environments in a way that would not be possible through recording devices and offer, for example, an understanding that goes beyond what could be audiovisually captured (Jenks 2020). Fieldnotes were focused in the sense that ethnographers, driven by the research questions of the project, looked at how the participants engaged and interacted, and captured the general characteristics of each setting in relation to the implementation of the educational commons (Jenks 2020). Simultaneously, the ethnographers' focus was stirred by participants' interactions, their decisions and collaboration, roles, and expression of their voices in these processes.

It is important to recognise that observation processes are selective (De Mañana 1981), in relation to access to spaces, research motivations, and the theoretical underpinnings of the research and the researcher. In this sense, observations were guided by the research questions within the context of the EU Horizon 2020 research project, e.g., how do participants engage in decision making, conflict resolution, participation;

example questions are mentioned in the Appendix. Furthermore, a researcher's field diary was kept, specifying, and documenting the contexts, actors, actions, and interactions seen, organising 'scenes' of the day (post-observation).

Semi-structured interviews and focus group interviews were also instruments used during the research. Informal meetings and conversations also took place with participants in the introductory stage of setting up the research. This did not produce data but allowed researchers to familiarise themselves with the context and build up trust with the participants, which was further established through prolonged engagement in the research environment. Semi-structured interviews provided researchers with valuable reflections on the case studies, while identifying topics that widen the available research dimensions. The preparation of the informal conversations or non-directive interviews included identifying themes for conversation, allowing participants to focus the discourses on one's own experience. Hence the conversation was never considered as a script of questions but as a 'social dialogical framework of discourse production between the researcher and the interlocutor, capable of inciting new thematic developments, free association of ideas, and evocations' (Devillard, Mudanó, and Pazos 2012, 368).

Table 1 below briefly summarises the research instruments used, their type, and scope, as also elaborated upon above. Using both participant-acquired data (interviews with children and facilitators) and researcher-created data (observations), triangulation was achieved; initial findings were also shared with participant teachers.

Table 1: Research instruments

Research Instruments	Type	Scope
Participant Observation	focused	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Contextualise data. b) Capture participants' behaviours and interactions
(Focus-Group) Interviews	semi-structured	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Capture participants' experience, thoughts, emotions b) Provide reflective space

Findings and Discussion

Our analysis has brought attention to the ways in which these two learning environments, VIVITA and Suvemäe-TKG, implement and promote the philosophy of the educational commons in multiple ways and, subsequently, the multiple intersections with the framework for student voice and participation. Our analysis has thus followed a deductive approach: how are educational commons and students' voice facilitated in these two contexts? To start with, the research team identified both implicit and explicit ways in which young people's agency and voice are boosted. For example, from an implicit perspective, VIVITA allows for enough autonomy to its participants through the 'free flow' activities of their choice, while encouraging their common decision-making and group work in community-based projects, like the 'Social Club'. Similarly, Suvemäe-TKG, being a democratic school within a public school, embeds the commons in the identity of the school explicitly by actively involving young people in the decision-making processes about the schools' activities and learning arrangements in an equal manner as staff does, while facilitating spaces and experiences for young people to assume responsibility for their learning and actions.

This section will discuss in depth the four elements of the Lundy model of participation (Welty and Lundy 2013) by describing how each of the elements is present in the two research contexts. The findings and discussion will always start by bringing empirical evidence from VIVITA, followed by Suvemäe-TKG. As described earlier, space and voice will address how children use specific scenarios to exercise their right to express their views, while audience and influence describe how children's views are given due weight in the two research contexts. Table 2 below summarises the mechanisms that are in place in each of the studied contexts to facilitate each of the four elements. These are further exemplified in the following subsections.

Table 2: Summary of how the elements of the Lundy model appear in the two research contexts.

Context	VIVITA (non-formal)	Suvemäe-TKG (formal)
Space	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Youth makerspace with various formats, including: ● ‘Free flow’ activities ● participation in curated and community projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Weekly meetings of staff and students ● Recurring meetings where opinions are heard, discussed and implemented
Voice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Working on individual and community projects ● Equal opportunities and support to express opinions and decide collaboratively. ● Recurring meetings where opinions are heard and discussed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Equal opportunities and support to express opinions ● Voting, consensus and consent procedures for decision making. ● Bottom-up approach to decision-making involving every member of the community
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engaging with peers, educators, parents, local / youth community, institutional authorities and stakeholders to implement projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Peers, parents, educators, school administrators and institutional stakeholders as audience of students’ projects
Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Responsibility of action towards themselves, external partners and the wider community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Responsibility of action towards themselves and the school/community

Space

Figure 3: VIVITA makerspace with safe and diverse opportunities for young participants to explore and realise their interests and goals, both individually and collectively. [Photo (left) by researcher; Photos (right and bottom) are courtesy of Tallinn Music Week and VIVITA, taken from: <https://vivistop-telliskivi.medium.com/tallinn-music-week-x-vivita-kids-festival-438451f9c488>]

More in detail and in relation to the Lundy model of participation, both learning environments create and maintain inclusive spaces and experiences for young people to be able to express themselves, propose solutions to the challenges perceived, and impact positively on their learning environments. In VIVITA, spaces such as the ‘free flow’ and community projects provide scenarios for young people to decide how to spend their time, find solutions and possibilities individually or collectively, and develop their skills within a caring and supporting environment.

These are some of the narratives that VIVITA’s facilitators shared when asked about participants’ experiences: ‘The kids were like, “I could talk to adults about my idea,

and I was listened to!” (quote from one of the educators referring to feedback from participants); ‘It takes a lot of trust to let your children come here. But these are the life skills that everyone should be getting’ (quote from one of the educators referring to the fact that VIVITA is a makerspace, so all kinds of tools are available for use for kids, under supervision and informed, but still, this idea is not necessarily easy to adjust to for many parents, adults) (Researchers’ diary 19/10/2021). Both quotes refer to young people’s feeling of safety that Lundy considers a fundamental element of the space (Kennan, Danielle, Brady, and Forkan 2019). Parents and other involved adults can play a significant role in ensuring access and giving consent to young people for their participation, making communication with adults and guardians as important.

Specifically, within the SMOOTH research process, when organising the kids’ music festival as part of the Social Club project, an interesting discussion emerged among the participants when discussing whether adults should be allowed or restricted from participating in the kids’ festival. Some young people expressed the need to not only claim ownership of a festival meant for kids but also to restrict this space for themselves only, highlighting how important it is for youth to not only have a space for themselves but also a space only for themselves, especially on the basis that it is organised by them and for kids. In other words, young people’s initial reaction was to exclude adults, possibly as a response to their continuous exclusion from decision-making processes (usually monopolised by adults). However, some other young participants disagreed and pointed out the need to include everyone in the project and that age should not be a criterion for exclusion in any case. Interestingly, this situation could be understood as an expression of oppositional identity, meaning that some young people adopt practices that challenge conventional practices, in this case through the exclusion of adults from the

decision-making process⁶. On the other hand, such discussion can be viewed as a positive sign of inclusion in the community on issues that matter. In this case, defining clear group boundaries is also one of the principles of commons, as described by Ostrom (1990).

In the other case study, Suvemäe-TKG's experience as a democratic school within a public-school places young people at the centre of the learning process. This involvement extends beyond academics to civic participation, achieved through specific times and spaces. Examples include the weekly meetings of the school community and personalised learning arrangements. These settings allow students to participate in shaping the learning experience, socialising worries and concerns, and finding solutions that address everyone's needs. All participants, whether youth or adults, are seated in a long room, occupying different chairs to eliminate observable hierarchy. Everyone is expected to raise their hand before responding or expressing a point of view. All views are heard and evaluated in terms of the community's interests. Similar procedures and spaces were followed for student participants and facilitators in the activities of the SMOOTH project.

Specifically, the SMOOTH project activities commenced with a collective brainstorming session, during which student participants shaped and pitched their ideas to their peers. Subsequently, participants explained and voted for their preferences, ultimately choosing to construct a kitchen island as their preferred project. Participants emphasised feeling safe when asking questions, motivating them to be more open to others' ideas. When Suvemäe-TKG youth were in charge of choosing and developing a project of their choice, their experiences in school life, particularly in terms of active

⁶ Oppositional identities have been conceptualised from the perspective of minority groups and homogenisation policies and practices; however, it could also be understood as the development of young people's attitudes that challenge conventional social and power roles within schooling environments. For more on this, see Bisin et al. (2011), Carter (2005) and Montouri (2006)

participation (e.g., listening to others, explaining their views, asking for help, etc.), served as a foundation for collaboration and support.

Both researched learning environments aimed to create spaces that facilitate the free expression of youth in a safe atmosphere. Building trust was identified as an essential component in consolidating such safe spaces for students' voices to be heard. Researchers also identified a progression in the way young people used and appropriated the space created by adults. This involved enacting their agency and creating new spaces to make decisions together with others, all while keeping in mind their shared goals.

Voice

Figure 4: The Kitchen Island designed and built by participants as a commoning process in Suvemäe TKG; photos by researcher.

Within the Lundy model, young people should have various opportunities to use their voices as members of a democratic community, expressing their views, feelings, and perceptions. This goal demands that safe and inclusive spaces provide the necessary

conditions to keep the discussions centred, enabling voluntary participation (or withdrawal) at any time, and ensuring access to information in order to enrich the discussion (Pechtelidis and Kioupkiolis 2020).

As observed in VIVITA's case study, kids organising a kids' festival within Tallinn's Music Week provides an example of how young people can claim their voice and participate actively in their community. Looking at the dynamics within the learning community itself, during the first meeting of young people who had volunteered to join the Social Club to co-organise the kids' festival, it came out that most of the participants already knew each other from other activities of the organisation.

Furthermore, learning to become more aware of one's own preferences and those of other learning community members presents an important part of life for the educational community. For this purpose, in the case of VIVITA, various tools have been used, including group discussions facilitated by the educator, individual thinking, and expressing one's ideas on post-it notes to serve as the basis for later common discussion, work in small task-based teams, common visioning, for example, to imagine how the planned festival should look alike, etc.

The participatory practices implemented at Suvemäe-TKG create opportunities for learners to propose and pitch ideas — intended to improve the school atmosphere, solve conflicts, plan activities and events, etc. — that will, in turn, be analysed by the whole school community. The same practice was witnessed during the research case study when the participants got into small groups and, one by one, proposed and explained different projects. Participants, having in mind both the democratic approach of their school and of the SMOOTH project, decided on their future actions through following commoning procedures. Peers and facilitators provided mechanisms for opinions to be

heard and considered. It is interesting that despite the plethora of ideas, every idea was to be considered by the members of the community, and that ‘everybody discussed with everybody’, as participants mentioned, facilitating thus inclusion for all.

Throughout both projects, VIVITA and Suvemäe-TKG, it seems clear that young people had diverse opportunities to use their voice in community life and reach meaningful changes needed. The ‘free flow’ (VIVITA) or non-formal learning arrangements (project-work in Suvemäe-TKG) provide young people with meaningful experiences to design their own individual learning projects based on their interests or get support whenever needed, truly personalising learning to each one’s needs.

Audience

Figure 5: Peers and educators as audience in VIVITA [Photo is courtesy of Tallinn Music Week and VIVITA, taken from: <https://vivistop-telliskivi.medium.com/tallinn-music-week-x-vivita-kids-festival-438451f9c488>].

For Lundy, an audience needs to be committed to taking young people’s views seriously; collectively identifying steps to achieve the desired change; lobbying before decision-making institutions and bodies; and confirming that the implemented change is aligned

with young people's views. In terms of the audience, VIVITA Social Club organising the kids' festival presents a very resourceful case, being engaged with multiple target audiences: (1) parents, families, and teachers from the schools that participants are attending, who have a role in relation to participants' ability to take part in such an educational process, even though it is based on their free will and voluntary decisions; (2) the wider youth community within VIVITA and in Tallinn city, the peers for whom the festival is organised; (3) Tallinn Music Week as an institutional audience creating an opportunity for youth to initiate and implement their own festival within the official framework of the Tallinn Music Week with its provided support; (4) educators in VIVITA who have a role in creating a facilitating educational context where young people can work to achieve their goal; (5) the wider community in the urban area where VIVITA is situated (called Telliskivi) and in Tallinn city, as the young people worked with several outside partners for the realisation of their idea, including (a) the musician they chose and contacted to perform as the main artist at their festival; (b) local companies to ask for their support with materials for decorating the festival facilities; (c) partnering with the local food truck company during the festival, and (d) establishing contact with the kids' program of the national TV to support wider dissemination of their initiative. All of these present examples of audiences that can have an impactful role for a youth initiative.

Suvmäe-TKG also provides examples of a variety of audience types within its practice. In relation to the Kitchen Island and Zen Garden projects that the youth worked on, the exchange below shows the variety of audience types, extending outside the close realm of the school community.

Researcher: Was there any moment when you got help from others?

Participant 3F: Yes, from the main school. The carpentry teacher helped us with the machines to cut the boards. Also, the architect helped us to make decisions and sketch

out the table so that we wouldn't mess up during the process.

[...]

Researcher: You mentioned you got help from outside of the school. Has this experience changed your opinion to work together with people outside of the school?

Participant 3E: I felt like it was impossible to collaborate with the main house, but it was a surprise that they were so helpful.

(Focus-group interview, Suvemäe-TKG)

In Suvemäe-TKG's case, similarly to what has been observed and identified in VIVITA, the audience is not a unified group of people but is composed of a diverse type of actors within – and outside of – the school community. To start with, within the framework of the school meeting, the audience (1) is composed of peers and adult facilitators who listen attentively to everyone's ideas, ask questions, and find solutions collectively. This type of audience, however, demands a preparatory process in which adults model and guide the participatory process with young people, making sure that every voice is listened to, respect is at the basis of communication, and the solutions benefit the common interests. Another type of audience (2) can be identified in families whenever decisions require their support to provide resources that will enable young people to advance in their plans and projects. Finally, the main school's administrators and teachers become an audience (3) when decisions involve coordination with the main school regarding academic possibilities, participation in events, or the development of projects within the school territory.

To conclude, the examples above allow the researchers to propose that, depending on the nature of the project, adults can act as experts and/or facilitators, ensuring that outside partners, parents, and other kids listen to others' views and engage in collective thinking. Similarly, whenever adults act as guides, they can advance in setting up the

conditions for other young people or adults/institutions to listen to and give feedback to the proposed ideas, engaging in a collective activity and strengthening social cohesion.

Influence

Figure 6: Young organisers of the Kids' festival in VIVITA interviewing the local singer and social media influencer, being filmed by the national TV [Photo is courtesy of Tallinn Music Week and VIVITA, taken from: <https://vivistop-telliskivi.medium.com/tallinn-music-week-x-vivita-kids-festival-438451f9c488>].

The educator approaches one of the Social Club participants in VIVITA with a proposal that there is a need to make a call to the kids' programme of the National TV to check if they would be ready to join the festival and film there, to feature it in their show later on (preliminary the info has been sent and the TV programme promised to consider). A participant is carefully asking additional questions from the educator (what to say and ask etc) and then practises 3-4 times, what and when to say exactly, non-verbally checking the feedback from the educator and researcher during that rehearsal process. Then, having received the phone from the educator, the participant rushes to make a call. Having finished, she is greatly excited, explaining that the TV crew is coming but expects more info on the programme and other details. She is so excited that jumps to hug the researcher

and the educator! She then goes and posts the info about it to WhatsApp chat for the others to know (Researcher's diary 27.04.2022).

As is evident from the extract above in the VIVITA case study, young people can claim leading roles and engage in decision-making with full commitment. Having been informed about the necessary action towards the national TV programme, a young participant takes the responsibility of representing the children's participation within the festival very seriously and with full responsibility over the planned impact-influence. Agency is not just an ability; it is also the belief that one can act in the world (Baker and Le Courtois 2022). Organising the festival itself provided the opportunity for youth in VIVITA to exercise their own (sense of) agency.

Hence, it is important to ensure that appropriate information, support, encouragement, and recognition are available both from peers and the closest adults, the educators, but also from families and teachers. Building youth's agency can be thinned or thickened in this respect (Jerome and Starkey 2022), which would mean withdrawing or offering support and protection as indicated by youth's needs and renegotiating interference throughout.

In the case of Suvemäe-TKG, the influence element is evident throughout the Kitchen Island construction project, as well as youth deciding by themselves for themselves and for the wider community. Hence, their voices were not only heard but also implemented, with the support of facilitators and external bodies, as mentioned earlier. Student participants were asked to reflect on the processes of this construction project, and in the below extract are some of their learnings:

Researcher: One thing you have learnt in this process?

Participant 3A: Maybe how to plan better... for example, we had to sketch the counter on the table so many times and I learnt how much planning it takes to make something

Participant 3F: I agree.

Participant 3E: I agree. I thought that if we had money, it would be easy to buy things, put it together and it's ready. but it is much more complicated.

Participant 3D: I also learnt how to communicate with the group. For some reason we have the need to do anything by ourselves, so I learnt more that it is ok to ask others for help.

(Focus-group interview, Suvemäe-TKG)

The interaction above illustrates the new skills and knowledge acquired through their involvement in this research project. As participants mention, having access to resources is not the only requirement for the success of a student-led project. It is also necessary to communicate with others in order to have influence, and for ideas to be not only discussed but also acted upon. Hence, influence comes both ways: the youth was able to create a legacy project for their community, but also how the community had an influence on the successful implementation of the project. Communicating well, but also asking for help, were the main steps towards achieving influence.

The element of educational commons that could be considered in alignment with the Lundy model of participation is that influence should not only remain a top-down approach, e.g. the community to listen and take action on youth's ideas. Influence should also come from the youth, in a bottom-up manner, and the youth equally have a responsibility to effectively communicate their needs, ask for help, and support in order for their voices to be acted upon.

Conclusion

Based on the two case studies implemented in Estonia, this article has focused on the one hand, on the interconnections between the elements of the Lundy model and commoning practices in education, and, on the other hand, the promotion of the student voice through

the implementation of the philosophy and practice of the commons within learning environments. In this sense, some major conclusions emerge from the case studies and discussions discussed above, presenting opportunities for the amplification of young people's voices within formal and non-formal learning environments.

On the one hand, the practice of a democratic school within a public school at Suvemäe-TKG has built a platform for young people to use their voice, share their ideas, address their concerns, and collectively create plans that benefit the community. Within this framework, young people are learning to explain their ideas, critically thinking about challenges and opportunities, and assuming responsibility in different ways. Furthermore, the horizontal organisation of the school meetings model, the active listening and critical thinking practices, make it possible for young people to consolidate a safe space to share with others who embody their participation as an audience to influence classmates and stakeholders, aiming at making their needs be heard, respected, and addressed while at the same time benefiting the school community as a whole. Finally, amidst adults' usual and repetitive narratives inviting them to assume responsibilities, young people become responsible—for themselves, their peers, and their community—when being directly involved in the decision-making process as equals. In this sense, youth decide for youth, enabling their assumption of the role of agents of change.

Similarly, VIVITA, as a creativity accelerator for young people, also provides safe spaces for youngsters to discover, display, and develop their creative ideas. From an individual perspective, young people engage in creative practices by sharing their voices and being actively supported by other youth and facilitators/educators (audience), who shift from a more conventional role of teachers and act not only as guides and companions but also as experts in modelling practices and supporting young people's projects. Within the development of personal or collective projects that are meaningful for them and the

wider community, young people find a supportive audience in various groups: facilitators, families, and local partners in order to consolidate an influence (i.e. Tallinn's Music Week), while developing agency for their own activities.

Clearly, it is the facilitators/educators' responsibility to provide safe spaces that support such engagement⁷, but their role becomes crucial when supporting young people to express their *voice*, making sure that an *audience* is receptive to their ideas, and lobbying for an actual impact (*influence*) within that process. Undoubtedly, the two case-studies provide meaningful insights into constructive relationships between learners and educators that are at the core for supporting multi-dimensional engagement of youth. In agreement with Lundy's model and supported by the evidence presented, this article confirms that safe spaces become the first fundamental step for students to feel free and comfortable to express their views and listen to others', develop argumentative and critical thinking skills, become empowered agents⁸ and consolidate their projects. However, to further activate students' agency, such spaces can be monitored — and maintained — not only by facilitators/educators but also by peers. In this sense, drawing from Vygotskian theory⁹ peers can support and/or monitor others as happened in different instances during this study. For this to happen, age segregation¹⁰ needs to be re-examined, as argued by Gatto (2002) and Van Horn (2003). Both cases of Suvemäe-TKG and VIVITA have demonstrated that whenever young people can interact in a safe environment and associate with each other based on shared interests, they identify ideas and projects that are relatable and meaningful to them, lead such projects with the aid of

⁷ For more on adult facilitation of safe spaces, see Fredricks (2011)

⁸ For a discussion on empowerment of young people, see Sara Baker and Soizic Le Courtois (2022)

⁹ For more on Vygotskian theory, see Hammond and Gibbons (2005)

¹⁰ the separation of children according to their age, which is one of the characteristics of modern schooling.

supportive adults, and practise active participation in both decision making and implementation processes, regardless of their age as determinant factor.

Finally, drawing on the examples and experiences above mentioned¹¹, the authors would like to highlight the complex mechanisms required for the actual democratic practices to be effective: in addition to the promotion, amplification and operationalisation of students' voice, a genuine democratic perspective needs to include and validate the facilitators' voices as equal peers in the democratic process. Also, we would like to highlight here that the shift from standardised curriculum and practices to more democratic ones is not always linear, but it needs to nourish from various experiences and adapt to local conditions by local participants. As a first step, we find that adding more common-based practices as the ones outlined earlier for student participation is one way forward towards a more democratic setting for learning.

Further research and limitations

This study explored, in situ, how two unique learning environments implement notions of the educational commons and cultivate student voice, engagement, and agency by providing appropriate spaces and support. The authors acknowledge that this study took place in just two learning environments in Estonia. As a result, we cannot draw generalisable conclusions for other environments that might be similar or dissimilar. Hence, the following is proposed.

The field of educational commons is niche, and it is yet to be explored in different contexts globally. This study offers a glimpse of how student voice and agency can be further reinforced following the practices applied in the two investigated contexts in

¹¹ For instance, the timetable negotiation, agreements regarding mobile devices and the youth-led organisation of the music festival.

Estonia. Investigating how such practices would work in other environments, also juxtaposing the differences between implementing the educational commons in formal and non-formal learning environments is crucial, as each context bears its own affordances and limits.

Aside from cross-cultural investigations and comparisons, further longitudinal work is needed to examine the impact of the commons and practices of cultivating student agency in the long term. Amplifying and operationalising student voice through the implementation of the commons challenges conventional schooling's goals, structures, and routines: how could we move away from rigid 'schooling' practices (standardised curricula, timetable, and hierarchical roles) and move towards emancipatory learning approaches? Based on our findings, regarding the multiple interconnections between the Lundy model and the educational commons, we consider these to be two coherent and complementary ways to move forward in regard to the need to advance in pedagogical practices that include young people to become agents of learning and social change, as argued by Ball and Collet-Sabé (2022, 995):

A recognition of students as independent ethical beings capable of reflection and decision-making and of taking responsibility for their identity and their social relations and at the same time accepting the necessity of failure, dissonance and conflict – a kind of consequentialist pedagogy.

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Appendix

Interview Questions:

- Which activities have you done during the case study? Describe them briefly...
- Do you think that the activities were linked to your interests and desires? Why? Why not?
- What is the single moment (positive or negative) that you'll probably never forget about this experience? Why?
- Describe how decisions were taken during group activities and by whom?
- Did you usually feel free to express your opinion openly? Why? Why not?
- Did you usually establish and share some specific rules, tasks, and roles during the activities? If yes, can you make some examples for me?
- Did you help others? and did they ever help you? If yes, can you make some examples for me? If not, can you explain better?
- Did the activities involve other people or places outside your classroom or youth organisation? If yes, can you make some examples for me?
- Did you help others outside the school/youth organisation? and did they ever help you? If yes, can you make some examples for me?